

Effect of Compromising Strategy on the Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

Authored by

Nnadi, Chikezie Sunday Onoh PhD^a, Igwe, Magnus Obiora^b

^aDepartment of Business Administration and Management, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu

^bDepartment of Institute of Peace, Conflict and Development Studies, Institute of Management and Technology, Enugu

Abstract

The study evaluated the effect of compromising strategy on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to; examine the effect of engaging in mindfulness activities on the output; and evaluate the effect of talking through conflicts with employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Three manufacturing firms were selected for study with a population of seven hundred and sixty five (765). Two hundred and eighty four (284) sample size was gotten using Ferund and William formula. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. Two hundred and thirty-eight (238) staff returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool. The findings indicated that Engaging in mindfulness activities had significant positive effect on the output, $Z(95, n = 238), 5.380 < 7.908, P < .05$ and talking through conflicts had significant positive effect with the employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. $Z(95, n = 238), 6.709 < 8.589, P < .05$. The concluded that engaging in mindfulness activities and talking through conflicts had significant positive effect with the employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study recommended among others that to improve mental stability and minimize negativity and stress in the food and beverage manufacturing firms there is need to be mindful of the activities that we do. It will encourage paying attention to thoughts, actions and body.

Keywords: *Compromising Strategy; Performance; Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms; Enugu*

Introduction

Compromise is described as being a win and loses agreement in which both parties get something of what they want but not all of what they want (Bankovskaya, 2019). Most disputes typically start with a competitive or collaborative strategy where the best possible outcome is the goal for both sides. However, a number of factors such as time requirements, financial costs, use of power and influence, and practical matters often enter into the equation. Omayo (2016) the realization that initial desired goals may be unachievable move parties to a negotiation process involving give and take in order to reach a compromised mutual agreement. Compromising strategy, Salleh and Adulpakdee (2018) typically calls for both sides of a conflict to give up elements of their position in order to establish an acceptable, if not agreeable, solution. This strategy prevails most often in conflicts where the parties hold approximately equivalent power. Business owners frequently employ compromise during contract negotiations with other businesses when each party stands to lose something valuable, such as a customer or necessary service (Ester, Wandiba & Olutayo 2020). Foods and Beverages manufacturing companies in Nigeria operate in a highly competitive environment hence; they require practicable strategies that will enhance long-term performance (Asenge, et al., 2023).

The increasing demand for product varieties by consumers and their continuous substitution has forced organizations to come up with strategies on how to improve performance. Irrespective of opportunities in the business environment, organizations face threats that distort their performance, hence increase the difficulty of survival. To survive and prosper in the competitive business environment, organizations need to build and sustain a workable strategy. Organizations have chosen from among several available strategic alternatives to make the best use of the available resources to reach predetermined goals thereby increasing performance (Oladimeji & Udosen, 2019). Compromise strategy enables that organization to effectively manage and resolve disputes arising from the employees very fast and stopping the possibility of escalating differences thus promoting a positive tolerant workplace culture (Lawrence-Chuku and Chima Onuoha, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

Compromise strategy is a conventional method for adapting to strife, concurring to a limited extent with the other individual's view or request. The most serious issue in building up the establishments of contention control in organizations is to build up an activity of plan to distinguish conflicts at its underlying stage. Compromise strategy fosters a give-and-take situation that focuses on addressing the concerns of each group. The parties involved are willing to work out their disagreements in a peaceful manner, with no one being considered a winner or loser.

Every organization encounter conflicts on a regular basis. Conflicts are unavoidable, but it can be managed in such a way of early detection. It is vital to keep track of the organizational signals that indicate the presence of conflict on a constant basis. If organization does not respond appropriately, there may have created a risk situation in which the conflicts can cause problem in the organization. However, the problem facing the study were; mindfulness activities; and employee sales volume. Conflicts as an independent variable of organizational behavior are also one of the more important predictors of productivity, work contentment, efficiency and performance. The goal of the compromise technique is to find a workable, if not mutually beneficial, solution by having both sides of a conflict give up some of their positions.

Organizations are faced by many challenges in an attempt to resolve conflict arising among its workforce. Most conflicts in manufacturing firms emerge from not satisfying its aggregate concurrence with its employees and as a rule persevere because of the methodology in dealing with the conflicts. However, bringing about employee setting out on mechanical activity which now and again results to attempt to manage or add up to action. The industrial actions by the employees ordinarily abandons them with a low spirit, decline in profitability, loss of gifted staff, loss of man and machine hours, turnover, increment in damaged items because of brought representatives responsibility down to work, and medical problems because of stress and depression. In this regard, the study evaluated the effect of compromising strategy on the performance of food and beverage companies in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of compromising strategy on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the effect of engaging in mindfulness activities on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State
- ii. Evaluate the effect of talking through conflicts with employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- i. What is the effect of engaging in mindfulness activities on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the effect of talking through conflicts with employee and sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study;

- i. Engaging in mindfulness activities has effect on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State
- ii. Talking through conflicts has effect with the employee and sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Significance of the Study

The study is significant because it helps enables organization to effectively manage and resolve disputes arising from the employees very fast and stopping the possibility of escalating differences thus promoting a positive tolerant workplace culture. The study helps in engaging employees to stay longer actively involve themselves in the workplace and produce better results.

Scope of the Study

The study focused the effect of compromising strategy on the performance. It was covered food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study examines on engaging in mindfulness activities on the output; and talking through conflicts with employee sales volume.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Compromising

Compromising is a way of reaching agreement in which each person or group gives up something that was wanted in order to end an argument or dispute (The Britannica Dictionary, 2023). A compromise in any situation is when an individual is willing to compromise in any disagreement. The intention of engaging in a compromise is to end the argument. Compromise is an agreement between two people where each person gives up a coveted desire to bring a close to the disagreement. A compromise is to have both sides make concessions and meet somewhere in the middle to end a dispute (Barowski & Kelly, 2023). Managing of conflict among the employees within the organization

in Nigeria is has been a challenge as a result of conflict which arises because of diverse composition of workforce which becomes difficulty for the human resource managers to effectively resolve (Kagwiria & Obere, 2019). Henry (2019) compromise strategy is a conventional method for adapting to strife, concurring to a limited extent with the other individual's view or request (Kagwiria & Obere, 2019). Conflict is inevitable in any workplace, especially when there are different opinions, goals, and interests involved (Cheryl, Donald & Gillon, 2024). Compromising in a conflict situation can have several benefits for both you and the other party. Compromising can also maintain or improve the relationship, while enhancing your reputation and credibility. In addition, it can foster creativity and innovation by encouraging you to consider different perspectives and solutions (Cheryl *et al.*, 2024).

Strategy

A strategy is the central rule of a framework, designed to unify all actions and decisions around busting the bottleneck to achieving the foremost aspiration (Blackwell, 2022). A business strategy is a powerful tool for helping organization reaches the business goals, defining the methods and tactics you need to take within the company. The business strategy also guides many organizational decisions, such as hiring new employees. A business strategy is an outline of the actions and decisions a company plans to take to reach its goals and objectives. A business strategy defines what the company needs to do to reach its goals, which can help guide the decision-making process for hiring as well as resource allocation. A business strategy helps different departments work together; ensuring departmental decisions support the overall direction of the company (Indeed Editorial Team, 2023; Igwe-Ukeorji, Orga, Mbah, 2023)). Business strategy is the strategic initiatives a company pursues to create value for the organization and its stakeholders and gain a competitive advantage in the market. This strategy is crucial to a company's success and is needed before any goods or services are produced or delivered (Boyles, 2022; Ugwu, 2020). The success of any business is determined by the effectiveness of the strategy it follows. A strategy explains how a company plans to compete in a market and how it intends to grow at a profit (Martin, 2023).

Compromising Strategy

A traditional way of dealing with conflict is to compromise which is agreeing partially with the other person's view or demand. This strategy prevails most often in conflicts where the parties hold approximately equivalent power, though ego clash and stated positions can hinder the ability to reach a compromise. Ndulue and Ekechukwu (2016) compromise strategy is a method of managing conflict which entails each party in the conflict situation surrendering certain value or interests in order to allow peace to prevail. The magnitude of the shortcomings of compromise depends on each conflict circumstances, environment and the extent of the compromise or values surrendered by each party in the conflict. For compromise to succeed it requires a reasonable level of assertiveness and willingness to collaborate (Ndulue and Ekechukwu, 2016).

Components of Compromising Strategy

Compromising is strategy, also known as reconciling, seeks a mutual agreement to settle a dispute (Herrity, 2023). The components of compromising strategy used in the study include; engaging in mindfulness activities; and talking through conflicts.

Mindfulness Activities

Mindfulness offers a solution, helping individuals stay anchored in the present moment, which reduces anxiety and promotes mental well-being. By encouraging clear thinking and emotional balance, mindfulness enhances essential skills like decision-making and problem-solving. Instead of promoting the common but flawed idea of multitasking, mindfulness advocates for focused attention, leading to fewer mistakes and better work output (Persona, 2023). When mindfulness is encouraged in the workplace, there's a palpable shift in how teams collaborate, characterized by genuine understanding and synergized efforts (Persona, 2023). Workplace mindfulness is the degree to which individuals are mindful in their work setting (Dane & Brummel, 2013). Mindfulness can be described as a present-focused consciousness (Hyland, Lee & Mills, 2015). Mindfulness includes paying close attention to both internal and external stimuli way (Hyland *et al.*, 2015). Positive workplace relationships can have a significant impact. They buffer

the effects of workplace stressors; promote thriving in employees, and foster communication, creativity and citizenship behaviors (Glomb, Duffy, Bono & Yang, 2012). By incorporating ways to practice mindfulness within organization, it can aid employees in discovering work-life harmony (Adam, 2023). Fostering a happy working environment that prioritizes ways to be mindful is most successful with the guidance of a happiness keynote speaker. This insightful expert will offer practical strategies on how to create a happy workplace and guide your mindfulness journey (Adam, 2023).

Mindfulness promotes positive social connections in the workplace through a number of integral mindfulness processes, but most especially empathy and response flexibility (Glomb, et al., 2012). Employee who practices being mindful are therefore more likely to show greater acceptance of colleagues without reactivity; optimal functioning of organizations is, in many ways, dependent upon positive interpersonal relationships. The way that mindfulness is implicated in workplace performance is dependent on the nature of the task, and the contextual factors of the work. Some mindfulness processes will beneficially affect a variety of types of job, whereas others are more specific (for example, for jobs with a lot of emotional content, decreased rumination and improved affective regulation may hold the key to performance) (Glomb *et al.*, 2012).

Talking through Conflicts

Conflicts are struggles that can arise during an active disagreement of opinions or interests, so it is important to understand how to navigate and resolve them. In the workplace, there are many instances in which conflict can happen between coworkers, and when it does, it is important to resolve the situation before it escalates (Igwe, Ede & Udeh, 2023). Conflicts are bound to arise at a workplace among employees at any time. However, the way you resolve the conflict can have an impact on the entire team. Unresolved conflicts can create a negative work culture, impacting employee retention, performance, and, ultimately, your company's bottom line. The key to resolving conflicts and fostering healthy relationships lies in the power of effective communication. Using the right communication strategies can transform conflict resolution, leading to understanding, reconciliation, and strengthened connections (James, 2023). Employees are bound to have disagreements from time to time. Whether it's a misunderstanding over who did what, a clash of ideas or a tangle of personal relationships, conflict is inevitable in any workplace. But how you handle those conflicts can make a world of difference to your company's success. There are several communication strategies employers, managers, human resources directors and employees can master to resolve workplace conflict successfully (Kiely, 2023).

Performance

Performance embodies the whole belief of the employee about their conduct and contributions to the accomplishment of the organization and compensation practices, performance evaluation and promotional practices are determinants of employee performance (Ahmad & Shahzad, 2015). It can be said that performance is affected by stress level and type. This relation can be explained through decrease and increase in work load (Hambuda, 2017; Ugwu, 2021), when the stress level is low, the worker's performance is sustained. When the worker is not exposed to stress while performing his/her duties, the performance is actually improved. Werang, Agung and Agung (2017) argue that the low stress stimulates workers and provides them with the incentive for better performance. Organizational performance refers to ability of business organizations to achieve stated goals such as profit, quality product, large market share, good financial results, and survival at predetermined time using relevant business strategy (Ghazzawi, 2018). Performance can be measured using objective or subjective self-reported measures. Nyagiloh and Kilika (2020) and Eze, Mbah & Oboko (2022) stated that the two significant measures of performance in organizations are non-financial and financial measures.

Components of Performance used in the Study

The five components of performance by Stanciu (2022) include; planning; monitoring; developing; rating; and rewarding (Stanciu, 2022). Planning, in planning the objectives are set during the planning phase, and the success metrics get defined. Monitoring, this is playing on the idea that what gets measured gets done, monitoring involves actively tracking and reporting the work done and potential hurdles. *Developing*, during the monitoring stage, under or over performance areas often come into focus, so development is when they get addressed; and *Rating & rewarding*: the last piece of the performance management process is comparing the outcomes against the goals set in the beginning. Now everything gets rated, and rewards and kudos are shared (Stanciu, 2022; Mbah, Nwatu & Okwor, 2021). However, the components of performance used in the study were output; and employee sales volume.

Output

Outputs are business results that may occur because of the inputs a company uses and implements. Outputs are usually quantifiable occurrences related to an organization's goals and objectives. A business's strategies, operations or processes may be able to influence or control them. Outputs can be markers that an organization's members can use as benchmarks in order to evaluate whether they are on track to meet their goal or ideal outcome. Outputs can be the direct and immediate results of a project. These results may be tangible or intangible, depending on the goals of the organization (Indeed Editorial Team, 2022). Outputs are the tangible or intangible things that an organisation or project produces. These could be completed services, products, interventions or other 'deliverables'. Outputs are the results of executing a project or an indication of what an organization has achieved in a defined course of a period. Products and/or solutions of a company are its outputs (UpRaise, 2024). The outputs are the actions or items that contribute to achieving an outcome (Magowan, 2019; Fred, Edeoga & Mbah, 2022). Output generally refers to the things produced. Output, in terms of the production unit means total number of products generated for a given duration and the various cost associated with the production. Outputs also refer to the number of customers visited in a given time. The organization needs to become accustomed, if there is a decline in the output of the organization due to alteration in the external or internal environment (UKEssays, 2018).

Employee Sales Volume

Sales volume refers to the number of units sold during a specific reporting period (Donny, 2022). The employee to sales ratio is simply a comparison between how many people you have to your sales volume. It is a measure of efficiency and ultimately profitability. The more you can increase sales without adding people, the more efficient you are. Sales volume refers to the number of units your company sells during a specific reporting period. This period could be a month, a quarter, or a year depending on what level of sales volume you are seeking to analyze. Investors frequently look at sales volume to assess the health of a growing or contracting company (Donny, 2022). Sales volume is a useful indicator for assessing the sustainability of your company. Sales volume is the total quantity of products that a business sells in a certain time frame. An organization's sales and marketing strategies could be efficient if there is a significant volume of sales. Along with revenue, many sales managers also regularly track sales volume. Sales volume measures how many products you are selling, whereas revenue measures the amount of income going into a business (Lystloc, 2022). Sales volume in business is the measure of how many products a company sells. It's the number of items a business sells over a specific accounting period, whether per month, per quarter or per year. Some larger businesses may measure sales volume on a per-day basis. The sales volume metric emphasizes the number of products that consumers purchase instead of the monetary profit earned by the company (Indeed Editorial Team, 2023).

Conceptual Framework used in the Study

A conceptual framework is a written or visual representation that explains the study variables and their relationships with each other. The starting point is a literature review of existing studies and theories about your topic (Natalie, 2022). A conceptual framework is a structure that provides a theoretical or conceptual foundation for research, allowing researchers to examine and analyze complex phenomena. It is a tool that researchers use to guide the research process by defining the key concepts, ideas, and theories that underpin their study (Salomão, 2023).

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Theoretical Framework

Conflict Management Theory

Theoretical framework of this research is the Conflict Management Theory developed by Mary Parker Follett (1933). She holds the view that conflict is inevitable in all organizations or societies where two or more people are brought together to achieve a pre-determined end. She explains that conflict is simply an exhibition of differences in ideas or opinions on given situations. Conflict could also be a display of different methodology of interpreting phenomena. Conflict to her arises as a result of different approaches to issues or different approaches to existing conflict resolutions. She opined that conflict could be good or bad or neither good or nor bad depending on the situation. Conflict also provides good or bad results or outcome depending on the manners it is interpreted, understand and resolved by the affected parties.

The study was anchored on this theory and in support with objective two of the study. The relevance of this theory (conflict management) is the fact that food and beverage firms consist of people who come together with the aim of achieving a given objective, as such conflict is inevitable in such a situation (Onyeizugbe, et al., 2018).

In support with objective one of the study, conflict theory holds that social order is maintained by domination and power, rather than by consensus and conformity. According to conflict theory, those with wealth and power try to hold on to it by any means possible, chiefly by suppressing the poor and powerless. A basic premise of conflict theory is that individuals and groups within society will work to try to maximize their own wealth and power (Adam, Robert and Kirsten, 2023).

Empirical Review

Talking through Conflicts with Employee and Sales Volume

Enyi, et al. (2022) conducted a study on evaluating the relationship between sales methods and technology, and physical expansion as strategies in managing shoplifting. The study was conducted at Enugu State, Nigeria. The study sought to evaluate the relationship between sales methods and technology, and physical expansion as strategies in managing shoplifting with South-East Nigeria. The study adopted survey research strategy. The finding shows that there is significant positive relationship between sales methods and technology in shopping malls and that there is significant positive relationship between sales methods and physical expansion of service in shopping malls. The study concluded that ICT directly affects how managers decide, how they plan and what products and services are offered in the shopping industry. The study recommended that where every employee is educated on theft prevention procedures, it will create a standard that everyone is held up to; and also creates a better work environment where there is confidence on every worker to help prevent losses in the shopping mall.

Bob-Fubara, Amah & Okocha (2022) conducted a study on compromising conflict strategy and workplace harmony in oil servicing companies in Rivers State. The study sought to examine the compromising conflict strategy and workplace harmony in oil servicing companies in Rivers State. The cross-section research design was adopted. Data was analyzed using Pearson product moment correlational coefficient. The finding shows that compromise as a dispute management strategy significantly impacts workplace harmony in oil servicing companies in Rivers State. The study concludes that dispute management through the use of compromise strategy significantly influence workplace harmony in relation to teamwork, and communication and this is able to the poor management activities among oil servicing firms. The study recommended that for the success of the organization and to get total committed workforce, management of oil servicing firms should ensure the goal of the organization are design such that, its achievement connect with visible strategy of dispute management.

Igwe, Ede and Udeh (2023) conducted a study on the effect of conflict management strategy on the productivity of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The objectives were to evaluate the effect of collaboration on the employee experience; and ascertain the effect of compromise on the ability to plan by the manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The population of one thousand two hundred and sixty-one (1261); and sample size of two hundred and ninety-five (295) was used. Data was analyzed using Likert Scale and Z – test. The findings showed that collaboration had significant positive effect on the employee experience; and compromise had significant positive effect on the ability to plan of the bakery manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study concluded that collaboration and compromise had significant positive effect on the employee experience of the bakery manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Talking through conflicts with Employee Sales Volume

Abubakar (2021) conducted a study on conflict management strategies: its impact on organization's goal attainment on selected manufacturing firms in Abuja. The study sought to identify the factors that causes; the types of conflict that are much consistence; the conflict management strategies adopted; and the effect of organizational conflict management on attaining of organizational goal in the manufacturing firms in Abuja. The sample size of one hundred and forty-five (145) was used. The study adopted Spearman correlation analysis. The findings showed that collective bargaining strategy displayed the highest significant positive correlation with organizational goal attainment. The study concluded that conflict is unavoidable in organization and could make or man organizational goal attainment depending on the conflict management strategies adopted. The study recommended that management should adopt an inclusive and collaborative strategy of conflict management as well as involving unions in making key strategic decisions to avoid conflict insurrection in the organization.

Olannye & Aliku (2022) conducted a study on enhancing employee performance through the application of dispute resolutions in the banking industry. The study sought to examine the effects of compromising strategy; and integrating strategy on employee performance in Delta State. The sample size for the study was one hundred and sixty-two (162) was used. The study adopted descriptive statistics and frequency analysis. The finding shows that there were positive and significant effects of compromising strategy and integrating strategy on employee performance. The study concluded that integrating g strategy has a major effect on employee performance in Nigeria's banking industry and Nigeria banks should improve on integrating strategy because it would go a long way in enhancing employee performance and that integrity in the banks could have been achieved through strong moral principles and moral uprightness in financial transactions. The study recommended that efforts should be made by management to organize seminars/workshops on organizational dispute resolution strategy from time to time for the employees.

Garba (2023) examined on the effect of corporate branding on sales volume of selected manufacturing firms in Kano State, Nigeria. The study sought to examine the relationship between brand associations and sales volume of manufacturing firms in Kano state, Nigeria. The population of this study is 1168 out of which a sample size of 369 was selected as sample size and a survey research design was employed. The study used multiple regressions. The findings showed that perceived quality significantly influences sales volume of manufacturing firms in Kano state, Nigeria. The study concluded that branding enable customers to distinguish between different products and services and recognize what they perceive satisfies their needs the most. The study recommended that manufacturing firms

should adopt brand awareness so as to ensure that customers' recall and recognize the brand as reflected by their ability and to identify the brand under different conditions which will promote firms' sales volume.

Methodology

The area of the study was Enugu State, Nigeria, effect of compromising strategy on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Three manufacturing firms were selected for study with a population of seven hundred and sixty-five (765). Two hundred and eighty-four (284) sample size was gotten using Fisher and William formula. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. Two hundred and thirty-eight (238) staff returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 84 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability coefficient of 0.77 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool.

Data Presentation and Analyses

The effect of engaging in mindfulness activities on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 1: Responses on the effect of engaging in mindfulness activities on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Anchoring in the present moment increases productivity	415	111	195	64	21	806	3.54	1.323	Agree
		83	37	65	32	21	238			
		34.9	15.5	27.3	13.4	8.8	100%			
2	Encouraging clear thinking promotes decision making and completed services.	540	148	117	70	19	894	3.76	1.369	Agree
		108	37	39	35	19	238			
		45.4	15.5	16.4	14.7	8.0	100%			
3	Enhancing emotional balance creates problem solving and improve products	445	148	168	62	25	848	3.56	1.376	Agree
		89	37	56	31	25	238			
		37.4	15.5	23.5	13.0	10.5	100%			
4	The employee focused attention promotes deliverable.	495	228	99	34	32	888	3.73	1.409	Agree
		99	57	33	17	32	238			
		41.6	23.9	13.9	7.1	13.4	100%			
5	Mindfulness led to fewer mistakes and better work output.	610	216	66	52	14	958	4.03	1.256	Agree
		122	54	22	26	14	238			
		51.3	22.7	9.2	10.9	5.9	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.724	1.3466	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1, 120 respondents out of 238 representing 50.4 percent agreed that anchoring in the present movement increases productivity with mean score 3.54 and standard deviation of 1.369. Encouraging clear thinking promotes decision making and completed services 145 respondents representing 60.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation of 1.369. Enhancing emotional balance creates problem solving and improve products 126 respondents representing 52.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.56 and standard deviation of 1.376. The employee focused attention promotes deliverable 156 respondents representing 65.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.73 and 1.409. Mindfulness led to fewer mistakes and better work output 176 respondents representing 74.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.03 and standard deviation 1.256.

The effect of talking through conflicts with employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 2: Responses on the effect of talking through conflicts with employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Fostering healthy relationships motivates the employees to sell more of the products.	475	272	54	84	15	900	3.78	1.307	Agree
		95	68	18	42	15	238			
		39.9	28.6	7.6	17.6	6.3	100%			
2	Using the right communication strategies transform conflict resolution and empower sales of the products.	535	296	57	18	29	935	3.93	1.334	Agree
		107	74	19	9	29	238			
		45.0	31.1	8.0	3.8	12.2	100%			
3	Resolved conflicts create positives work culture and promote marketing strategies.	650	248	54	20	18	990	4.16	1.205	Agree
		130	62	18	10	18	238			
		54.6	26.1	7.6	4.2	7.6	100%			
4	Non escalation of conflict reduces stress and promotes healthy growing of the business.	580	292	39	42	30	983	4.07	1.210	Agree
		116	73	13	21	15	238			
		48.7	30.7	5.5	8.8	6.3	100%			
5	Handling conflicts makes a world of difference and enhanced the organizational sales.	440	352	39	64	17	912	3.83	1.258	Agree
		88	88	13	32	17	238			
		37.0	37.0	5.5	13.4	7.1	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.354	1.2628	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2, 163 respondents out of 238 representing 68.5 percent agreed that fostering healthy relationships motivates the employees to sell more of the products with mean score 3.78 and standard deviation of 1.307. Using the right communication strategies transform conflict resolution and empower sales of the products 181 respondents representing 76.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.93 and standard deviation of 1.334. Resolved conflicts create positives work culture and promote marketing strategies 192 respondents representing 80.7 percent agreed with mean score of 4.16 and standard deviation of 1.205. Non escalation of conflict reduces stress and promotes healthy growing of the business 189 respondents representing 79.4 percent agreed with mean score of 4.07 and 1.210. Handling conflicts makes a world of difference and enhanced the organizational sales 176 respondents representing 74.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.83 and standard deviation 1.258.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Engaging in mindfulness activities has effect on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

		Anchoring in the present movement increases productivity	Encouraging clear thinking promotes decision making and completed services.	Enhancing emotional balance creates problem solving and improve products	The employee focused attention promotes deliverable.	Mindfulness led to fewer mistakes and better work output.
N		238	238	238	238	238
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.349	.454	.374	.416	.513
	Positive	.088	.080	.105	.134	.059
	Negative	-.349	-.454	-.374	-.416	-.513
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		5.380	7.001	5.769	6.417	7.908
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from 5.380 < 7.908 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that engaging in mindfulness activities had significant positive effect on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from 5.380 < 7.908 against the critical Z- value of 0.000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that engaging in mindfulness activities had significant positive effect on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Hypothesis two: Talking through conflicts has effect with the employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

		Fostering healthy relationships motivates the employees to sell more of the products.	Using the right communication strategies transform conflict resolution and empower sales of the products.	Resolved conflicts create positives work culture and promotes marketing strategies.	Non escalation of conflict reduces stress and promotes healthy growing of the business.	Handling conflicts makes a world of difference and enhanced the organization sales.
N		238	238	238	238	238
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.435	.511	.557	.544	.489
	Positive	.063	.122	.076	.063	.071
	Negative	-.435	-.511	-.557	-.544	-.489
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		6.709	7.876	8.589	8.394	7.552
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $6.709 < 8.589$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that talking through conflicts had significant positive effect with the employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.709 < 8.589$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that talking through conflicts had significant positive effect with the employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Discussion of Findings

From the result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z- value ranges from $5.380 < 7.908$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000, which implies that engaging in mindfulness activities had significant positive effect on the output food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result, Enyi, et al. (2022) conducted a study on evaluating the relationship between sales methods and technology, and physical expansion as strategies in managing shoplifting. The finding shows that there is significant positive relationship between sales methods and technology in shopping malls and that there is significant positive relationship between sales methods and physical expansion of service in shopping malls. Bob-Fubara, Amah & Okocha (2022) conducted a study on compromising conflict strategy and workplace harmony in oil servicing companies in Rivers State. The finding shows that compromise as a

dispute management strategy significantly impacts workplace harmony in oil servicing companies in Rivers State. Igwe, Ede and Udeh (2023) conducted a study on the effect of conflict management strategy on the productivity of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The findings showed that collaboration had significant positive effect on the employee experience; and compromise had significant positive effect on the ability to plan of the bakery manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

From the result of hypothesis two, the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.709 < 8.589$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000, which implies that talking through conflicts had significant positive effect with the employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result, Abubakar (2021) conducted a study on conflict management strategies: its impact on organization's goal attainment on selected manufacturing firms in Abuja. The findings showed that collective bargaining strategy displayed the highest significant positive correlation with organizational goal attainment. The study concluded that conflict is unavoidable in organization and could make or man organizational goal attainment depending on the conflict management strategies adopted. Olannye & Aliku (2022) conducted a study on enhancing employee performance through the application of dispute resolutions in the banking industry. The finding shows that there were positive and significant effects of compromising strategy and integrating strategy on employee performance.

Conclusion

The concluded that engaging in mindfulness activities and talking through conflicts had significant positive effect with the employee sales volume food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Compromising can be seen as a cooperative and pragmatic approach to conflict, as it shows respect for the other's perspective and willingness to find a common ground. Compromising can be useful in situations where the conflict is not very important or complex, and where a quick and temporary solution is needed. Compromising can also be helpful when the parties have equal power and similar goals, and when they value their relationship more than their individual interests.

Recommendations

The study recommended the following as on the findings:

1. To improve mental stability and minimize negativity and stress in the food and beverage manufacturing firms there is need to be mindful of the activities that we do. It will encourage paying attention to thoughts, actions and body.
2. The management should endeavour to resolve conflicts through proper communication that can lead to high-functioning and more satisfying relationships in all aspects of life.

References

- Abubakar, H.A. (2021). Conflict management strategies: its impact on organization's goal attainment on selected manufacturing firms in Abuja. *Journal of Global Economics and Business*, 2(7), 111-126.
- Adam, H., Robert, C.K. and Kirsten, R.S. (2023). *Conflict theory definition, founder, and examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/conflict-theory.asp>
- Adam, M. (2023). *4 ways to adopt mindfulness to engage your team*. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/4-ways-adopt-mindfulness-engage-your-team-adam-markel#>
- Ahmad, S., & Shahzad, K. (2015). HRM and employee performance: A case of university teachers of Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK) in Pakistan. *African journal of business management*, 5(13), 5249.
- Asenge, E.L., Okadimeji, A.T., Enyi, L.A. and Adudu, C.A. (2023). Effect of turnaround strategies on firm performance in Nigerian foods and beverages manufacturing industry: A study of BUA Foods Plc. *International Academy Journal of Management, Marketing and Entrepreneurial Studies*, 10(1); 120-127.
- Bankovskaya, V. (2019). *Development of conflict management strategies to increase the organizational effectiveness in Nordic companies* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Barowski, J. & Kelly, M. (2023). *What does it mean to compromise in any situation?* Retrieved from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/compromise-definition-examples.html>.
- Blackwell, M. (2022). *What is the definition of strategy?* Retrieved from <https://arkaro.com/we-definition-of-strategy/>
- Bob-Fubara, I., Amah, E. & Okocha, B. F. (2022). Compromising conflict strategy and workplace harmony in oil servicing companies in Rivers State. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 7(8), 1-5.
- Boyles, M. (2022). *What is business strategy & why is it important?* Retrieved from <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/what-is-business-strategy>
- Cheryl, S., Donald, M., Gillon, D.L. (2024). *What are the pros and cons of compromising in a conflict situation?* Retrieved from <https://www.link/advice/1/what-pros-cons-compromising-conflict-situation>
- Dane, E., & Brummel, B. J. (2013). Examining workplace mindfulness and its relations to job performance and turnover intention. *Human Relations*, 67, 105 – 128.
- Donny K. (2022). *Sales volume: Definition, formula, and how to increase it*. Retrieved from <https://www.zendesk.com/blog/sales-volume/>
- Enyi, T. C., Agbaeze, E. K., Eze, F.O., Obayi, P. M., Asogwa, A. P., Ugwu, D. C. & Mbah, P. C. (2022). Evaluating the relationship between sales methods and technology, and physical expansion as strategies in managing shoplifting. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(7), 1-15.
- Ester, T., Wandiba A. & Olutayo K. O. (2020). Compromise and employee performance in Kampala capital city authority (KCCA), Uganda. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 8(3); 1-10.
- Eze, F.O Mbah P.C & Oboko, Winny Chinonso (2022) Organisational Competency and the Performance of Academic Staff of State Tertiary Institutions in Enugu State. *Advanced Journal of Current Research* 7(7) 27-48
- Eze, F.O, Edeoga N.W., & Mbah, P.C., (2022) Human Resource Planning and Organizational Performance of National Human Right Commission in Nigeria, *Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences* 6 (5) 1-21
- Garba, S.M. (2023). Effect of corporate branding on sales volume of selected manufacturing firms in Kano State, Nigeria. *UMYU Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 5(1):28-38.

Nnadi, C. S. O. & Igwe, M. O. (2024). Effect of Compromising Strategy on the Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State. *Contemporary Journal of Management* 6(1), 1-17.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10688566>

- Ghazzawi, I. A. (2018). Organizational turnaround: A conceptual framework and research agenda. *American Journal of Management*, 17(7), 10-24.
- Glomb, T. M., Duffy, M. K., Bono, J. E., & Yang, T. (2012). Mindfulness at work. *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management*, 30, 115 – 157.
- Hambuda, F. N. (2017). *Job satisfaction and job performance during the implementation of a performance management system: the case of a Namibian municipality* (Doctoral dissertation, Cape Peninsula University of Technology).
- Henrrity, J. (2023). *5 conflict resolution strategies: steps, benefits and tips*. Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/conflict-resolution-strategies>
- Henry, O. (2019). Organizational conflict and its effects on organizational performance. *research journal of business management*, 2 (1), 16-24.
- Hossain, Z. M. (2017). The impact of organizational conflict on employees' performance in private commercial banks of Bangladesh. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 1(9).
- Hyland, P. K., Lee, R. A., & Mills, M. J. (2015). Mindfulness at work: A new approach to improving individual and organizational performance. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, (8); 576 – 602.
- Igwe, M. O., Ede, T. E. and Udeh, S. I. (2023). Effect of conflict management strategy on the productivity of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. *Advance Journal of Current Research*, 8(7); 1-13.
- Igwe-Ukeorji, S., Orga, C. C., Mbah, P. C., (2023) Risk Management Strategy and Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing firms in Enugu State. *Journal of Business Research and Statistics* 5 (2), 30-50
- Mbah, P.C., Nwatu E.C., & Okwor, E.O., (2021) "Compensation and employee performance of Deposit Money Banks in South East, Nigeria" *International Journal of Research Management (IJRM)*11(3)2249-5908
- Indeed Editorial Team (2022). *Differences between inputs vs. outputs (with definitions)*. Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/inputs-vs-outputs>
- Indeed Editorial Team (2023). *10 business strategy examples (and why it helps to have one)*. Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/business-strategy-examples>
- Indeed Editorial Team (2023). *What is sales volume? (plus how to calculate it yourself)* Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/what-is-sales-volume>
- Iqbal, N., Anwar, S., & Haider, N. (2015). Effect of leadership style on employee performance. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5(5), 1-6.
- James, W. (2023). *The power of effective communication in conflict resolution*. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/power-effective-communication-conflict-resolution-james-weaver>.
- Kagwiria, B. & Obere, E. (2019). Compromise strategy and performance of telecommunication industry in Kenya. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 7(1), 221-223.
- Kiely, K. (2023). *Workplace conflicts? 5 tips to improve communication*. Retrieved from <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/8766-resolving-workplace-conflicts.html>
- Lawrence-Chuku, J. and Chima Onuoha, B. (2022). Organizational flexibility and corporate performance of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Management Practice*, 2(1); 1-13.
- Lystloc (2022). *What is sales volume?* Retrieved from <https://www.lystloc.com/blog/what-is-sales-volume-and-how-to-use-sales-volume-effectively-to-get-revenue/>

Nnadi, C. S. O. & Igwe, M. O. (2024). Effect of Compromising Strategy on the Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State. *Contemporary Journal of Management* 6(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10688566>

Magowan, K. (2019). *Outcomes vs outputs: What's the difference?* Retrieved from <https://www.bmc.com/blogs/outcomes-vs-outputs/>

Martin, H.(2023). *What is strategy? Definition, components & examples explained.* Retrieved from

Natalie (2022). *Conceptual and theoretical frameworks for thesis studies: what you must know.* Retrieved from <https://www.enago.com/thesis-editog/conceptual-and-theoretical-frameworks-for-thesis-studies-what-you-must-know>

Nyagiloh, K. A., & Kilika, J. M. (2020). Theoretical review of turnaround strategy and its organizational outcomes. *International Business Research*, 13(2), 13–34.

Oladimeji, M. S. & Udosen, I. (2019). The effect of diversification strategy on organizational performance. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 11(4), 120–131.

Olannye, P.A. & Aliku, I.H. (2022). Enhancing employee performance through the application of dispute resolutions in the banking industry. *Journal of Global Social Sciences*, 3(12), 47-74.

Omayo, F. M. (2016). *The role of interpersonal communication in managing peer co-worker conflict in a nongovernmental organisation: a case study of SILC Kenya, Eldoret* (Doctoral dissertation).

Onyeizugbe, C.U., Aghara, V., Olohi, E.S., & Abaniwu, P. C. (2018). Industrial harmony and employee performance in food and beverage firms in Anambra State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research*,6(6), 22-35.

Persona (2023). *Embracing mindfulness in the workplace.* Retrieved from <https://www.dfulness-in-the-workplace>

Salleh, M. J., & Adulpakdee, A. (2018). Causes of conflict and effective methods to conflict management at Islamic secondary schools in Yala, Thailand. *International Interdisciplinary Journal of Education*, 1(217), 1-13.

Salleh, M. J., & Adulpakdee, A. (2018). *Causes of conflict and effective methods to conflict management.*

Salomão, A. (2023). *The significance of conceptual framework in research.* Retrieved from <https://mindthegraph.com/blog/conceptual-framework-in-research/>

Stanciu, T. (2022). *The components of performance management: 4 handy examples.* Retrieved from <https://mirro.io/blog/components-performance-management/>

The Britannica Dictionary (2023). *Compromise.* Retrieved from <https://www.bary/compromise>.

Ugwu, F.I. (2021), Effect of Employee Career Development and Performance of Lectures in State Universities in South East, Nigeria. *Contemporary Journal of Social Science and Humanities* 2 (4) 1-19.

Ugwu, F.I. (2020). Effect of Collaboration Strategy on the Performance of Small Business in Enugu State. *GE-International Journal of Management Research* 9 (11) 48-69.

UKEssays. (2018). *Organizational output of Pfizer.* Retrieved from <https://wnt/organizational-output.php?vref=1>

UpRaise (2024). *Output Vs outcome.* Retrieved from <https://upraise.io/blog/output-vs-outcome-top-10-differences/>

Werang, B. R., Agung, A. A. G., & Agung, G. (2017). Teachers' job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and performance in Indonesia: A study from Merauke District, Papua. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 6(8), 700-711.

APPENDIX

Effect of comprising strategy - paulinus 2024

R/Q1	Effect of engaging in mindfulness activities on the output of food and beverages manufacturing firm in Enugu.	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Anchoring in the present movement increases productivity					
2.	Encouraging clear thinking promotes decision making and completed services.					
3.	Enhancing emotional balance creates problem solving and improve products					
4.	The employee focused attention promotes deliverable.					
5.	Mindfulness led to fewer mistakes and better work output.					
R/Q2	Effect of talking through conflicts with employee sales volume of food and beverages manufacturing firm in Enugu.					
6.	Fostering healthy relationships motivates the employees to sell more of the products.					
7.	Using the right communication strategies transform conflict resolution and empower sales of the products.					
8.	Resolved conflicts create positives work culture and promotes marketing strategies.					
9.	Non escalation of conflict reduces stress and promotes healthy growing of the business.					
10.	Handling conflicts makes a world of difference and enhanced the organizational sales.					